

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Full paper

STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

All papers published in this conference proceedings have been peer reviewed through a peer review process administered by the proceedings Editors. Reviews were conducted by expert referees to the professional and scientific standards expected of a conference proceedings.

Proceeding Editors

Nicolas Robinson-Garcia
Daniel Torres-Salinas
Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado

Citation: Sjögarde, P. (2022). Exploring user needs in relation to algorithmically constructed classifications of publications: A case study. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti2212). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6959252>

Copyright: © 2022 the authors, © 2022 Faculty of Communication and Documentation, University of Granada, Spain. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#).

Collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/sti2022grx/>

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Exploring user needs in relation to algorithmically constructed classifications of publications: A case study¹

Peter Sjögarde*

*peter.sjogarde@ki.se

Health Informatics Centre, Department of Learning, Informatics, Management and Ethics
Karolinska Institutet
University Library, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

Introduction

Citation networks have been used since the 1960s to analyze research publications, for example to explore how research fields evolve and are delineated into sub-fields (de Solla Price, 1965; Garfield, 1963; Garfield et al., 1964). In the recent decade, large scale classifications of research publications have been created by clustering in citation networks (see e.g. Boyack, 2017; Boyack & Klavans, 2014; Sjögarde & Ahlgren, 2018; Waltman & van Eck, 2012). I herein refer to such classifications as algorithmically constructed publication-level classifications (ACPLC).

Little is known about the information need of potential users of ACPLCs. Many have pointed out that there is no one classification that can be used for all purposes (Glänzel & Schubert, 2003; Gläser et al., 2017; Klavans & Boyack, 2017; Mai, 2011; Smiraglia & van den Heuvel, 2013; Velden et al., 2017; Waltman et al., 2020; Waltman & van Eck, 2012). The choice of methods must therefore be guided by the intended use of an ACPLC. Nevertheless, there has not been much discussion about utilization of ACPLCs and how different ACPLCs correspond to different information needs in research organizations. Furthermore, user studies and case studies are missing.

In this case study I have studied the use of an ACPLC in a university management setting. I studied how an ACPLC can be used to support the promotion of an emerging research field, focusing on the information needs in a project at Karolinska institutet (KI) called AI@KI. KI is a large medical university with about 3,000 employed researchers and more than 2,000 PhD students. The aim of AI@KI was to strengthen medical research applying artificial intelligence (AI), both in clinical and preclinical settings. To do so, AI@KI aimed to identify AI research at the university and to improve the internal communication between researchers engaged in medical research using AI.

The aim of the current study was to explore and evaluate the usefulness of an ACPLC to managers of AI@KI. I focused on management information needs, interpretability of an

¹ This work was supported by The Foundation for Promotion and Development of Research at Karolinska Institutet.

ACPLC and how the ACPLC corresponded to the information needs. The users being persons in leadership roles at the university and the project leader of AI@KI.

Method

I interviewed three of the managers of the project. All three also hold management positions at the university. Thereby, they mediate the information need of the university related to the development of AI activities. The interviews were semi-structured, following a short questionnaire of open questions. The video conference software Zoom was used for the interviews. The interviews focused on the context and aim of AI@KI as well as the information need related to the project. The interviews took around 30 minutes each.

Two interviews were conducted with the project leader. The first focused on the context, aim, information need and the role of the project leader (similar to the interviews with the management). The second interview was conducted after providing bibliometric data to the project leader. It focused on the use of an ACPLC and how that responded to the information need in the project. The second interview was supported by the bibliometric data and the respondent used his screen to explain and support his answers.

All questionnaires used for the interviews are presented in the supplementary material. The interviews were analyzed following a thematic structure. I analyzed each theme (for example the information needs related to the project) separately by listening to relevant parts of each recording. I noted key statements related to the theme, for example “there was no picture of how many researchers are working with, or think they are working with, or say they are working with something that can be called AI or machine learning. There was no map [...]” [translated from Swedish]. The results presented in this paper is a summary of these statements.

Bibliometric data were provided to the project manager during the project. The bibliometric data were based on AI publications retrieved from a search query. The search query is provided in the supplementary material as well as a description of the process to obtain it. The query was delimited to the publication period 2016-2021 and was conducted 1 July 2021. It resulted in 78,519 publications, of which 353 had a KI author address.

The bibliometric data included a list of KI publications retrieved from the search query, publication counts per year for KI and for the whole publication set, a co-occurrence network of MeSH, a co-authorship network of KI researchers, a bipartite co-occurrence network of KI researchers and MeSH and map of clusters in an ACPLC. The cluster map contained the levels of disciplines, specialties and topics and was obtained using the Leiden algorithm in a citation network (Traag et al., 2019). The process to determine granularity levels, create labels and visualize the ACPLC has been described in previous papers (Sjögårde, 2021a; Sjögårde et al., 2021; Sjögårde & Ahlgren, 2018, 2020). The 2021 April update of the NIH Open Citation Collection was used for clustering (Hutchins et al., 2019). The classification is available in figshare (Sjögårde, 2021b) and interactive maps of clusters are available in Github.²

² The map of AI research in biomedicine is available at <https://petersjogarde.github.io/papers/ai/world/index.html> [2022-01-14]
The map of AI research in biomedicine restricted to KI is available at <https://petersjogarde.github.io/papers/ai/ki/index.html> [2022-01-14]

Results

Context and aim of AI@KI

The respondents described the situation before AI@KI as scattered, with no overall picture of AI activities at KI, lack of communication between research groups, lack of central support in AI related issues and large differences in competence and stage of development. This situation is common in premature areas. It was recognized that KI needed to gather information and connect researchers to be able to develop a more focused and systematic strategy for AI at the university. The managers of AI@KI emphasized that such strategy includes both research and the process to implement AI methods in clinical practice. The respondents saw a high unfulfilled potential of AI methodologies in the clinical setting for diagnoses, treatment, and prevention. Furthermore, they saw several barriers for AI methodologies to reach the clinical practice, such as juridical issues, skepticism, and lack of technical, analytical, and ethical competences. They considered researchers to be in need of more support to be able to take AI from basic research all the way to clinical practice. The connection between AI and precision medicine was emphasized by the respondents.

The aim of AI@KI was to improve competence, enhance communication between researchers, develop support structures and get an overview of the use of AI at KI. The aims related both to AI implementations in basic research and clinical practice.

The respondents expressed that there was a need to enhance the competence of researchers using AI, for the researchers to better formulate research questions, to choose suitable AI methods, and be more successful when applying for grants. They saw a need of more structured approaches when using AI at the university. There was also a need to increase general awareness of AI in all parts of the university, from students to management.

Enhanced communication between researchers was seen as a means to increase the competence of individual researchers using AI or facing research problems that are suitable to be addressed by AI. Furthermore, collaboration was emphasized as a way to develop more systematic approaches to implement AI and to get synergy effects by joining different competences. The respondents considered better communication to be a way to connect competences in order to develop more and better AI related education at the university as well as avoid redundancy. There was also a need to bring researchers together to be able to run large projects and find resources.

Support structures were needed to help researchers at various stages in the research process, such as formulation of research questions, choice of AI methods, ethical considerations, judicial and regulatory issues, finding collaborations etc. There was no clear picture of how the support structure would be organized at the university. Some expressed that a centre or core facility might be created as a result of the project, but they pointed out that no such decision had been made. Another possible path forward was a less centralized support structure, based on communication and networks between different units, but without a centralized organization. The horizontal communication between researchers was emphasized in several interviews and that AI must be integrated into the entire university.

An overview of the use of AI at KI was needed to be able to develop activities related to the other aims of the project. Information about *who* is doing *what* within AI was seen as essential to connect researchers with shared interests. This information was also considered important for researchers in early stage of implementing AI. Such researchers need to know where to find the right competences, for example to get training and find collaborators with

more experience. Another aspect mentioned was the accessibility to structured data. Information about AI activities was seen as crucial for researchers to be able to share data or to develop standards. Furthermore, information about the AI activities was needed by KI for external communication. It was expressed that there was a need for KI to be prepared in order to take part of large investments related to AI and to participate in, and contribute to, external collaborations.

Use of the bibliometric data

Activities within AI@KI had been ongoing before the bibliometric data was provided to the project leader. These activities had mainly focused on interviews with researchers using AI and a seminar series. Researchers were reached by an ad hoc social networking strategy. The project leader had contacted researchers known by the project managers. More researchers had been reached through these researchers and other social contacts. The seminar series were also announced, and a growing number of researchers were added to the email list of the seminar series. The project leader expressed that this strategy was not very structured and risked being biased towards researchers known beforehand. However, a more structured strategy was out of scope for the project.

The bibliometric data was used to complement the picture that had arisen from the interviews and the seminars. This was principally done in two ways:

(1) The bibliometric data were used to *support the qualitative* work and to find new areas of AI research to be explored. The project leader used the bibliometric data to find new persons to interview that were not known from previous work. He also found new articles that were relevant to his work in the project. This use of the bibliometric data was integrated with the qualitative work and affected this work.

(2) The bibliometric data was used to *get an overview* of AI research at KI. It made it possible to display “the ecosystem of AI research” at KI and give a “taxonomy” of this system. This overview was considered to be broader and more comprehensive than the picture given from the qualitative work. For example, the project leader (and several managers) expressed that there was a common perception that AI in medicine is mostly about using AI for image interpretation, for example in cancer imaging and diagnoses or prediction of cognitive impairment from MRI. However, the cluster map showed that AI at KI was much broader and diversified, for example that AI was extensively used for textual and numerical data besides imaging.

The interpretation of the cluster map took some effort and was sometimes challenging. The project leader found the labels to be helpful, but not always enough to interpret the contents of a cluster. The hierarchy and the zooming capability helped the respondent to relate a cluster to its parent, siblings, and children. This information was helpful in interpreting the contents of the cluster. It was rather easy for the respondent to interpret the areas that he was more familiar with than areas which he was less familiar with. He also underlined that he found the relations between areas as interesting and useful.

The grouping of publications into clusters appeared as logical to the respondent. Nevertheless, he stressed that exploration was needed to interpret the clusters. A relatively large cluster of computational biology was mentioned as an example. To understand the contents of this cluster he had to navigate between the underlying specialties, reading labels, the additional provided terms, and the lists of underlying topics. Another example was the division of psychiatry into two different areas (labeled “alzheimer disease; dementia; psychiatry” and “psychiatry; public health; suicide”). Some exploration was needed for the respondent to

interpret how the clusters differed. He found this division to be logical, but considered the areas to be overlapping.

Conclusions

I have studied users' information needs in a project aiming to strengthen collaboration and competence of AI related activities at KI. An important information need in the project was to get knowledge about *who* is doing *what* within AI. This information was essential to build efficient support structures, improve communication and collaboration and increase competence. The overall goal of AI@KI was to develop a more focused, structured, strategic and professional use of AI at the university.

The case study exemplifies how ACPLCs may support managers at universities by providing information about the topical structure of research output that reflects research activities. The ACPLC-based cluster map was useful in the project to complement other activities, including supporting qualitative work, such as interviews and social network building. Furthermore, it provided overview and displayed the research of interest. The ACPLC led to a wider perspective on AI at the university and helped the project to reach researchers in a broader range of research fields.

The study showed that it is challenging to interpret the contents of clusters. Interpretation of clusters was supported by the possibility to get both overview and detail in the visualization of the ACPLC. The possibility to navigate from broad disciplines down to narrow topics and retrieve individual publications helped the project leader both to understand topics and to find articles of interest. Thereby, this navigation improved the utility of the ACPLC. Nevertheless, interpretation of ACPLCs are challenging.

This study has provided some insights into user needs and applicability of an ACPLC in practice. To my best knowledge this is the first study of this kind. Knowledge about users' information needs is essential to evaluate and improve the usefulness of ACPLCs in a research management setting. Because of the low number of participants, no general conclusions can be made regarding the usefulness of the ACPLC. Further user studies are needed to evaluate the usefulness of ACPLCs and the interpretability of clusters in relation to information needs in universities.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my gratitude to the respondents.

Funding information

Peter Sjögarde was funded by The Foundation for Promotion and Development of Research at Karolinska Institutet.

References

Boyack, K. W. (2017). Investigating the effect of global data on topic detection. *Scientometrics*, *111*(2), 999–1015. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2297-y>

Boyack, K. W., & Klavans, R. (2014). Including cited non-source items in a large-scale map of science: What difference does it make? *Journal of Informetrics*, *8*(3), 569–580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2014.04.001>

de Solla Price, D. J. (1965). Networks of Scientific Papers. *Science*, *149*(3683), 510–515. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.149.3683.510>

Garfield, E. (1963). Citation indexes in sociological and historical research. *American Documentation*, *14*(4), 289–291. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.5090140405>

Garfield, E., Sher, I., & Torpie, R. J. (1964). *The use of citation data in writing the history of science*. <https://doi.org/10.21236/ad0466578>

Glänzel, W., & Schubert, A. (2003). A new classification scheme of science fields and subfields designed for scientometric evaluation purposes. *Scientometrics*, *56*(3), 357–367. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1022378804087>

Gläser, J., Glänzel, W., & Scharnhorst, A. (2017). Same data—different results? Towards a comparative approach to the identification of thematic structures in science. *Scientometrics*, *111*(2), 981–998. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2296-z>

Hutchins, B. I., Baker, K. L., Davis, M. T., Diwersy, M. A., Haque, E., Harriman, R. M., Hoppe, T. A., Leicht, S. A., Meyer, P., & Santangelo, G. M. (2019). The NIH Open Citation Collection: A public access, broad coverage resource. *PLOS Biology*, *17*(10), e3000385. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000385>

Klavans, R., & Boyack, K. W. (2017). Which type of citation analysis generates the most accurate taxonomy of scientific and technical knowledge? *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, *68*(4), 984–998. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23734>

Mai, J. (2011). The modernity of classification. *Journal of Documentation*, *67*(4), 710–730. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00220411111145061>

Sjögårde, P. (2021a). Improving overlay maps of science: Combining overview and detail. *ArXiv:2110.07917 [Cs]*. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2110.07917>

Sjögårde, P. (2021b). PubMed Classification. Version 1. *Figshare*. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.5610971.v1>

Sjögårde, P., & Ahlgren, P. (2018). Granularity of algorithmically constructed publication-level classifications of research publications: Identification of topics. *Journal of Informetrics*, *12*(1), 133–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.12.006>

Sjögårde, P., & Ahlgren, P. (2020). Granularity of algorithmically constructed publication-level classifications of research publications: Identification of specialties. *Quantitative Science Studies*, *1*(1), 207–238. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00004

Sjögårde, P., Ahlgren, P., & Waltman, L. (2021). Algorithmic labeling in hierarchical classifications of publications: Evaluation of bibliographic fields and term weighting approaches. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, *72*(7), 853–869. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24452>

Smiraglia, R. P., & van den Heuvel, C. (2013). Classifications and concepts: Towards an elementary theory of knowledge interaction. *Journal of Documentation; Bradford*, 69(3), 360–383. <http://dx.doi.org.ezproxy.its.uu.se/10.1108/JD-07-2012-0092>

Traag, V. A., Waltman, L., & van Eck, N. J. (2019). From Louvain to Leiden: Guaranteeing well-connected communities. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 5233. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41695-z>

Velden, T., Boyack, K. W., Gläser, J., Koopman, R., Scharnhorst, A., & Wang, S. (2017). Comparison of topic extraction approaches and their results. *Scientometrics*, 111(2), 1169–1221. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-017-2306-1>

Waltman, L., Boyack, K. W., Colavizza, G., & van Eck, N. J. (2020). A principled methodology for comparing relatedness measures for clustering publications. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(2), 1–23. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00035

Waltman, L., & van Eck, N. J. (2012). A new methodology for constructing a publication-level classification system of science. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 63(12), 2378–2392. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.22748>